

Luc Montagnier maverick of Sciences: Free, maverick(1), multidisciplinary and aesthete of research

Tribute to Jean Claude Perez

(1) In an art, a science, in any group, a person who acts in isolation with complete independence from others.

What an adventure !

Luc Montagnier § J.C Perez August 2020

One day in the summer of the year 2019, Luc telephones me, he asks me to start a bioinformatics research with him on the analysis of the waves of this prohibited research: "the memory of water". To sum up, from the blood plasmas of patients suffering from pathologies such as Lyme disease, alzheimer's disease, autism or HIV, the high-dillion technology produces traces of DNA via PCR: are these PCR primers relative to the DNA sequences of certain soil bacteria like herbaspirillum or Sutterella? Could these bacteria be implicated as a co-factor in these new chronic illnesses that Luc called "cold infections"?

In his brilliant intuitions, Luc was already seeing very, very far:

here is its precise scientific objective (mail of July 2019):

“Hello, I start my answer again, this dirty machine having apparently erased everything. I reminded you of our main goal, the neutralization by antiphases of signals emitted by the DNA of pathogenic agents. »

By enthusiastically accepting this collaboration, I did not know that I was going to share almost every day of the last 3 years of the research of one of the greatest scientists of the century...

Retrospective:

But to fully understand how this melting pot of interdisciplinary research capable of changing the paradigm was set up, let's go back 34 years: in 1988...

So what happens in this memorable year 1988 which will see the merger of disciplines as diverse as computer science, physico-chemistry and genetics... all this to perhaps one day revolutionize medicine?

Luc Montagnier, he fights with the American Robert Gallo by articles of Science or Nature interposed on this burning subject honorarily but above all financially: which of them two (and of their 2 respective countries) is the "legitimate father of the discovery of the virus HIV?". The battle for the paternity of the AIDS virus was tough, here is what Luc wrote to me on October 5, 2021 about Professor Fauci who played a major role in both the HIV epic and the COVID-19 epic:

“As for the Fauci fraud in AIDS, I ask to see the evidence. There has been a long scientific discussion on the role of the virus in the disease since practically finished because the reduction of the viral load by tritherapy saves the CD4 and saves the life of the patient, whether he is hemophiliac or homosexual.

The difference between the Gallo/Fauci group and me is that I add to the virus an intracellular activator which is a bacterial co-factor. Gallo's fraud was to use my virus by giving it another name which brought it closer to retroviruses oncogenes when I brought him proof that it was a lentivirus. Where was Fauci in this? He was the fundraiser for Gallo's lab and I learned later that he was blocking the research of Ruscetti and his associate. ..LM »

In this same year of 1988, when the promising Artificial Intelligence (I.A) swears among its majority researchers only by the intelligence of the left brain, that of formal and logical reasoning called "expert systems", I go against the current with the track of the right brain by publishing my book "New paths towards Artificial Intelligence: multidisciplinary, self-organization and neural networks".

My neural network called "fractal chaos" is hypersensitive, close to holographic memory (waves already) where "the whole is the sum of the parts and where each part is a summary of the whole". This machine is even able to "get bored" by detecting repetitive situations to such an extent that an article in the journal Sciences et Vie headlined about it "you forgot to unplug me"! This machine, while getting bored, would therefore detect a situation of impasse and would be able to "change the paradigm"!

In particular, its hypersensitivity is such that it continues to recognize an image whose luminosity would have been attenuated in a ratio of 10000...

So when in 1988 Jacques Benveniste with "his memory of water" speaks of high dilutions at $10E120$, with a lot of imagination we can link this phenomenon with my small dilutions of information in a computer, certainly more modestly, at $10E4$!

As I am a free researcher (IBM research center), I will therefore see Jacques Benveniste in his INSERM lab in Clamart to discuss this analogy. And so we became friends. Who would have imagined then that it would be Luc Montagnier who would one day extend this discovery by extending it to DNA via this magnificent technology that is PCR...

In 1988 again began in a completely different field, genetics, this pharaonic and global project HUGO which will last more than 20 years: the project of sequencing of the 3 billion base pairs TCAG constituting the human genome...

Alan Turing: “Why are there Numbers in Nature?”

What is the relationship between these 3 areas?

When I try to understand the hypersensitivity of my network of I A Fractal Chaos, I discover that the network positions its fractals in numerical regions close to the golden number 1.618.

But everyone knows that the ratio of 2 successive Fibonacci numbers 1 1 2 3 5 8 13 21 34 55 89 144... for example 34 and 21) tends towards the inaccessible limit of Phi, the Golden Number.

Fibonacci Numbers are ubiquitous in Nature: Nautilus shell, numbers of pineapple spirals (, sunflower flowers, palm trees, artichokes or pine cones...

I then have this intuition: it is necessary to look for Fibonacci proportions between the TCAG nucleotides of the DNA: for example if 55 successive bases are divided into 21 TC and 34 AG, I will note a "resonance"... over and over again waves!

“Shifting Paradigm”:

With this discovery I was going to abandon Artificial intelligence to embed myself as a maverick in a hostile world: that of biologists and geneticists...

What do numbers and mathematics have to do with a world as serious as genetics?
The researchers to whom I present my discovery look down on me.

A French Nobel Prize for Medicine director of the lab with which I validate my discovery will even kindly tell me "you must have fun with all that"!

Apart from a group of open-minded biologists, only Luc Montagnier will take my research very seriously. Thus, on September 22, 1993, Luc Montagnier organized a conference for me at the retrovirus pavilion of the Pasteur Institute in order to present my methods and results.

In the article "La Musique des Gènes" published in 1995 in Sciences et Avenir, he wrote "... the principle of Jean-Claude Pérez's discovery interests me, it is very possible that beyond the sequences, a sort of "DNA supercode" exists...". It is therefore to Luc that I owe the baptismal name of this discovery "The SUPRACODE of DNA"... (see <https://fr.scribd.com/doc/262257532/1st-April-1995-SCIENCES-et-AVENIR-Magazine-La-Musique-des-Genes-avec-the-opinion-of-Professor-Luc-Montagnier>).

It was around this same time that Luc founded the World Foundation for AIDS, the FMPRS, at UNESCO because, like my Fractal Chaos system capable of getting bored, Luc understood that research on AIDS will only find a way out if it changes the paradigm by adopting a multidisciplinary approach. This is how he will propose to participate in this approach far beyond Medicine to illustrious researchers such as the mathematician René Thom or the Belgian Nobel Prize in Chemistry Ilya Prigogine...

So from 1993 until 2019, many years pass, Luc Montagnier, faithfully, will help me here and there: conferences, publication of articles and...

And we arrive in 2019... Waves in the DNA...

Our bioinformatics analysis of PCRs associated with water memory waves gives encouraging results.

Towards the end of 2019, we begin to develop a theoretical explanation in which the waves that I discover through my theoretical approach to the Master Code would be preserved when substituting oxygen ghost hexagons (OH) of the DNA trace in water, for CONH hexagons of real base pairs TC or AG. Luc Montagnier will give me the following preface to this article on the Master Code:

PREFACE by Professor Luc Montagnier

After the discovery of the DNA double helix structure allowing both the stable storage of genetic information and its transfer through messenger RNA to protein synthesis organelles themselves structured by RNA most abundant in cells, the ribosomal.

This wonder of nature exists in ALL living beings from the virus to humans and is based on two codes, the linear sequence of nucleotides and that derived from codons where three nucleotides allow with a certain flexibility - identical codons - the choice in the twenty amino acids.

But we are missing a third CODE the one governing at multicellular beings from the rotifer to human, the stabilized modulation of gene expression in a nutshell the differentiation of cells from the single cell of the fertilized egg.

It is logical to think that this program which begins as soon as fertilization is written in the DNA.

We are also prone to associate it with non-coding DNA sequences although they control gene expression.

I introduce here the notion developed by Jean-Claude Pérez of mathematical harmony, a higher order present in all living beings and whose existence it finds in genomes, including those of viruses.

Thus, the natural evolution of variants of the genome of coronavirus Covid 19 tends towards increasingly long Fibonacci series.

It remains to determine the Who, the How and the Why of such developments.

I will bet with my mathematician colleague that waves and fractals play a role ...

Luc Montagnier

Perez, J.C., & Montagnier, L. . (2021). SIX FRACTAL CODES OF LIFE FROM BIOATOMS ATOMIC MASS TO CHROMOSOMES NUMERICAL STANDING WAVES: THREE BREAKTHROUGHS IN ASTROBIOLOGY, CANCERS AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE. International Journal of Research-GRANTHAALAYAH, 9(9), 133–191.

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The epic of COVID-19:

Then in the midst of this promising research on the waves of DNA fingerprinting by water, a tsunami of new research overwhelmed us from the end of January 2020: the adventure of COVID-19 which will occupy us for 2 years and 7 items...

Luc's first battle: "the manipulated origin of the SARS-CoV2 virus genome".

It was during the month of January 2020 that the genome of the SARS-COV2 virus was accessible to everyone on the internet.

Immediately, we analyze this sequence demonstrating by the waves of the Master code its increasing adaptation to the human host, thus since the SARS of the 2000s the standing waves were increasing over Fibonacci periods gradually increasing from 13 (SARS), then 21, then 34 for SARS-CoV2.

But above all we suspected a small region of 1% of the genome (300 UCAG bases) which seemed to be exogenous, therefore possibly coming from laboratory manipulation.

In particular we wrote:

"Finally, we ask ourselves the question of a possible artificial origin of this genome, in particular because of the presence of fragments of HIV1, HIV2 and SIV retroviruses."

As Luc will say in his historic intervention of April 17, 2020 on Cnews "it is almost a watchmaker's job"!

This article was published on PREPRINTS from the beginning of February 2020 and obtained a good audience.

Curiously he was censored on February 17, 2020 only 24 hours after informing the French Minister of Health of this information which seemed major. Of course this synchronization was surely the result of chance.

The article was then published in an Indian newspaper: Jean-Claude PEREZ. (2020). WUHAN COVID-19 SYNTHETIC ORIGINS AND EVOLUTION. International Journal of Research - Granthaalayah, 8(2), 285–324. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3724003>

This assertion will know a world radiation when on April 17, 2020 Luc presents these results on television. Indian researchers who demonstrated the same thing also saw their article censored. Treated as false and conspiratorial in 2020, the comments on the manipulated nature of this virus are in 2022 recognized and accepted as almost certain. This is what "Le Point" published the day after Luc's interview:

"Once again, the eminent Professor Luc Montagnier, Nobel Prize in Medicine for the co-discovery of the AIDS virus, supports a scientific theory against the grain of the entire scientific community. With his friend of thirty years, the mathematician Jean-Claude Perez, he claims that the Sars-CoV-2 virus (responsible for the Covid-19 epidemic) was artificially manufactured by injecting fragments of the HIV virus into a coronavirus in a laboratory in Wuhan.../...It's the work of a sorcerer's apprentice, continues the 88-year-old Nobel Prize winner.

Luc's second big battle was summed up by "it is the covid19 vaccines that create the variants".

Already in his tv interview of April 19, 2020 based on an article that we were going to publish 3 months later, Luc Montagnier explained how the virus had already started to get rid of certain exogenous regions of its genome.

This means that if we had not started testing and developing vaccines in England, South Africa, Brazil and India by 2020, the virus might have died out by 2020. But this is not a chance if the 4 variants that would emerge come respectively from these 4 countries (ALPHA, BETA, GAMMA and DELTA variants).

Luc's ultimate third battle: "risk of fatal neurodegenerative Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease emerging soon after COVID-19 vaccine."

From the end of December 2021, we are publishing an article with Valère Lounnas demonstrating that, unlike ALL the variants and all the vaccines, only the OMICRON variant has managed to completely get rid of the Prion region of the Spike protein of the virus. However, we continue to vaccinate with a vaccine constructed from a sequence still comprising, in 2022, this Prion.

Luc prefaces our article thus:

Addendum "A big step towards the understanding of Nature. Your work allows us to hope that we will soon emerge from the nightmare into which the cretinoid branch of Humanity is plunging us".

After having discovered a case of Creutzfeldt-Jakob by the media (it was the first case referenced "Doyer princeps"), Luc, faithful to the Hypocratic oath today trampled and flouted, asks me to get in touch with this family remembering an antioxidant treatment that he experimented on prions nearly 20 years ago.

Thus, on November 20, 2021, Luc wrote to me: "The ANSM trick: there is no recognized declaration of CJD because those which occur after vaccination evolve too quickly to be a sporadic CJD.. Their small brain cannot or does not want to imagine that after 2 injections of Pfizer mRNA which CARRIES in its sequence a PRION ready to associate with a homolog carried by the ACE receptor (Têtz work 2020), things can go much faster and in two months lead to death. It is iatrogenic CJD caused by excess mRNA going to the brain. LM".

And it was then that his final battle began: to try to cure this disease and to write with the neurologist Claire Moret-Chalmin and myself this article analyzing several dozen cases where the first symptoms of this fatal disease appeared ten days after vaccination. !

Luc will not have known of the publication of this article, however, on February 1, 2022, at 8 p.m., he telephoned me to discuss it, on February 2, the same with the neurologist: even joking on the telephone, in both cases he omitted mischievously to tell us that he was already hospitalized!

Luc will therefore have remained a researcher even in his hospital bed.

Also, out of respect for the importance he attributed to this final article, our duty today is to finalize and publish it.

Luc feared indeed that beyond the dozens of deaths due to this disease identified in a few days, this disease may not reach tomorrow the millions of children on whom this useless vaccine is imposed.

Here is the preprint version of this article:

“Towards the emergence of a new form of the neurodegenerative Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease: Sixteen cases of CJD declared a few days after a COVID-19 “vaccine” Jab”

February 2022 DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14427.03366

• Claire Moret-Chalmin Luc Montagnier jean-claude Perez

• DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.14427.03366

Aesthetics and Research...

A Sunday afternoon. One day in the summer of 2021. Luc calls me... I go out to my garden because the brainstorming is going to be long... While we speculate on the harmony of the sars-cov2 genome or maybe on DNA waves, Luc suddenly interrupts me "I hear a bird singing!". It's a blackbird from my garden. So our discussion drifts to the aesthetics and harmony of birdsong...

Luc could only love music. Because with any great researcher, the aesthetic sense remains inseparable from the process of discovery. It is certainly the driving force behind it. I remember that day in 1994 when, in his office at the Pasteur Institute, we listened together to my CD of "La première Musique des Gènes"... Luc wondered about the evidence of this musical harmony of the sequences of the DNA of the KI-RAS oncogene or the HIV genome of AIDS. Thus, to these 3 rare qualities of the exceptional researcher which are freedom, the fact of going against the current, and the lucidity of the change of paradigm by going to dig in other disciplines, it was necessary to add this sense of aesthetic. Luc combined these 4 exceptional qualities... And it is for this simple reason that the memory of the history of science, tomorrow, will elevate Luc Montagnier to the very top of the podium of the great discoverers of the 20th century...

And I would have had the immense privilege of living and sharing every day for almost 3 years his beautiful and brilliant intuitions. Regrets? Sure! Luc left too quickly... Of course beyond our shared passions for research, I had time to appreciate his great humanism, his questions about the mystery of life: God or great architect or just self-organizing? One of his biggest questions to which he will not have had time to find an answer is that of the

MYSTERY OF CELL DIFFERENTIATION:

He often challenged me on this central question: in 2021 Luc wrote to me: "I don't know not if you received my question on Beijing but I continue: to find the differentiation codes we assume that the viruses already have some that they have stolen from the cells they infect. This is therefore the case with our Corona.

Two possibilities: RNA or peptides. So search the RNA genome for coding or non-coding sequences aimed at modifying the outer covering of the virion (its "differentiation"), for example the spicules...or their number, the icosahedron construction..."

If Luc admired these laws of life, he was more pessimistic about humans and the future of humanity. But I wouldn't have had time to discover and share his fine sense of humor, or even self-mockery...

